

A study into the Performance and Efficiency Effects of using High-Ethanol Fuel in a Conventional Spark Ignition Engine

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1. Abstract

The aim of conducting this project was to understand the benefits and drawbacks of varying the Ethanol content in the fuels used in conventional spark ignition combustion engines. The objectives of this assignment were to run a baseline test using conventional E10 pump gasoline fuel on a standard consumer engine made by Ford. This was done using engine dynamometer equipment in order to measure the torque and power output produced. A replica engine model was produced for simulation purposes using Ricardo WAVE software. Once baseline figures were obtained from these two methods of study, further testing was conducted. Initially a parametric study was carried out on the WAVE software in order to verify that the results produced were realistic and produced usable data for comparison purposes. The parametric study was conducted through varying the length of the intake runners in 10mm increments to observe the effect on the peak torque figures as well as the shape of the torque curve. Once satisfied with the credibility of the values being produced, the study proceeded in simulation and real-world testing methods.

The study was conducted with experimental testing and software simulation running in tandem with each other in order to try and replicate the environments as closely as possible. The literature study carried out beforehand strongly suggested an expected increase in power and torque values produced by running an engine on high-Ethanol fuels rather over regular pump fuel, and for this reason E10 and E85 fuels were chosen for study. This was due to E10 being the conventional fuel readily available at the pump, and E85 being typically the highest Ethanol blend available before crossing the line into typical "race fuels". Without revealing the specifics about different engine types and performance modifications to accompany the change in fuel, general literature suggests that E85 fuel provides performance benefits across the board with the main drawback being the extra volume of fuel required to meet comparable performance values or distances covered in the vehicle.

After obtaining baseline power and torque trends for both real-world and simulation environments, the next steps were to run further engine dyno testing and compare the results with the simulation equivalent. Due to limitations involving health & safety of the user and nearby students, as well as maintaining the longevity of the engine and dyno equipment, testing was limited to 4,000RPM. This limitation was then replicated in the simulation environment alongside running full speed tests in the safe computer-based environment in order to study any affects this might have on the data.

Engine dyno testing and WAVE simulations were carried out for various throttle openings (as allowed by the dyno capabilities), the results were then plotted for both cases. The next phase of testing included a modification to both the engine's ECU software, as well as the WAVE model in order to accommodate for the change in fuel being used. Once complete, further tests were run on E85 similarly as with the E10 fuel.

In summary, the results of the experiment in the real-world testing environment opposed the expected outcome of greater performance when using high-Ethanol fuel. However, in the simulation environment the results confirmed the literature theory. Several reasons for this are considered immediately as mentioned later in the report, mainly being the limitations of the hardware and software capabilities associated with the engine and dynamometer, as well as the potential for tuning errors that may be apparent due to the lack of a professional ECU calibration expert. Further to these reasons, the engine WAVE model may have been too simplistic in its construction, therefore not allowing for the full potential of the fuel to be apparent during simulations. This is in terms of fuel properties such as burn duration, as well as ignition temperatures.

2. Nomenclature

AFR – Air to Fuel Ratio

BHP – Brake Horsepower

BTDC – Before Top-Dead Centre

BTU – British Thermal Units

CI – Compression Ignition

CO₂ – Carbon Dioxide

DAS – Data Acquisition System

Dyno – Dynamometer

E5 – 5% Ethanol-Gasoline Blend

E10 – 10% Ethanol-Gasoline Blend

E85 – 85% Ethanol-Gasoline Blend

ECU – Engine Control Unit

EMF – Electromotive Force

GHG – Greenhouse Gas

HC – Hydrocarbon

IC/ICE – Internal Combustion/Internal Combustion Engine

IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

kW – Kilowatt

MAP – Manifold Absolute Pressure

Nm – Newton-Metre

OEM – Original Equipment Manufacturer

RON – Research Octane Number

RPM – Revolutions per Minute

SI – Spark Ignition

Sim – Simulator

Stoich – Stoichiometric Ratio

TPS – Throttle Position Sensor

UK – United Kingdom

USA – United State of America

VE – Volumetric Efficiency

WOT – Wide-Open Throttle

3. Introduction

With the world currently dependant on fossil fuels in most areas of industry, the concern regarding the permanent damage caused to the environment is ever-growing. (ClientEarth, 2022) explains that the burning of fossil fuels releases large amounts of carbon dioxide and greenhouse gases. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) states that 89% of global CO₂ emissions were a result of fossil fuels and industry, as of 2018. With this in mind alongside the ever-decreasing supply of finite energy resources, many vehicle manufacturers are researching and experimenting with alternative sources of energy. This has caused a large increase in electric and hybrid vehicles being manufactured, as well as interest growing in areas such as Hydrogen fuel-cells and Hydrogen combustion engines. As (NationalGrid, 2022) explains, the infrastructure to accommodate a solely electric automotive industry is not currently in place. This means that until such a time comes, a combination of energy sources is required to be used for vehicle propulsion. For this reason, this project investigates the benefits and possibilities of running renewable, hydrocarbon-free fuels as a substitute, such as Ethanol, with a key focus on comparing E10 and E85 fuel blends.

4. Background Theory

4.1 What is Fuel?

'Fuel', as defined by (Merriam-Webster, 2023) is "a material used to produce heat or power by burning". This definition is ideal for explaining the role of fuel when considering an internal combustion engine. The fire triangle (also known as the combustion triangle), as shown below by (Scutum, 2023), illustrates the composition of elements that must be present in order for the chemical reaction required to result in combustion. With the fuel aspect covered, the next element to consider is the "Heat", which can be achieved through various means when considering the internal combustion (IC) engine. For the purpose of this particular study, this is achieved by the spark plug initiating the burn, hence being deemed the "Spark Ignition" engine. Lastly, the final piece of the puzzle being oxygen. This is obtained from the ambient air surrounding the engine, as free air is made up of approximately 21% Oxygen according to (NASA, 2016).

Figure 1 - Combustion Triangle - Scutum (2023)

4.2 Hydrocarbon Combustion

Further to the basic combustion principles explained above, Hydrocarbon Combustion is of greater interest when discussing the topics of IC engines. (Energy Education, n.d.) explains this as the chemical reaction where a hydrocarbon reacts with oxygen to form carbon dioxide (CO₂), water, and heat. Hydrocarbons being an organic compound composed exclusively of hydrogen and carbon atoms, as explained by (Fernando, 2022).

The diagram below illustrates an example of hydrocarbon combustion and the resultant by-products of the reaction.

Figure 2 -Sample of Hydrocarbon Combustion Chemical Equation - (Energy Education, n.d.)

The general equation below is used to balance chemical equations involving hydrocarbon combustion:

Where:

X – the number of carbon atoms in the hydrocarbon

Y – the number of hydrogen atoms in the hydrocarbon

N – the number of oxygen atoms required in the hydrocarbon combustion reaction

One key observation from the above equation is that CO₂ is always produced, regardless of the type of hydrocarbon molecule. As fossil fuels have varying compositions from one another, their hydrocarbon molecule size varies as well. As an example, Natural Gas comprised mostly of Methane (CH₄) is the smallest hydrocarbon molecule, whereas oil has larger molecule compositions, followed by coal which have the largest and most complex hydrocarbon molecules. As a result of this, different hydrocarbons have different ratios of hydrogen to carbon, and therefore produce different ratios of water to CO₂. As a general rule, the longer and more complex the molecule, the higher the ratio of carbon to hydrogen. And for this reason, different quantities of carbon will be yielded from burning equal amounts of different hydrocarbons. As a result of this, coal inherently releases more CO₂ than burning an equal mass of oil or natural gas, due to the higher quantities of complex hydrocarbon molecules.

4.3 Research Octane Rating (RON)

The next key area of importance to consider when investigating the fundamentals of an SI engine is the Research Octane Rating or “RON” associated with the fuel in question. This octane rating as explained by (Stolark, 2016) is a measure of the fuel’s resistance to cause “knock” or pre-detonation in an engine. Knock occurs when fuel is ignited prematurely within the cylinder, this degrades

efficiency and more importantly can be detrimental to engine components. Some typical RON grades that can be found at petrol stations within the UK can range from as low as 91 to as high as 99. The higher the octane number, the greater the resistance to detonate.

The benefits of a higher RON rating means that manufacturers/engine builders can take advantage of the fuel properties available to enhance engine performance through several methods, not limited to: higher compression ratios, greater boost pressures through turbocharging/supercharging, as well as running more advanced ignition timing, according to (Mach1, 2023). The combination of the aforementioned methods allows for better fuel efficiency, safer and cleaner running engines, and enhanced performance with greater power output. (Mach1, 2023) also states that the only prominent drawback of using a higher-octane fuel is the inherent cost increase over using a lower rated alternative.

4.4 Ethanol

As (Stolark, 2016) explains, using Ethanol as a fuel in the automotive industry stems back to Henry Ford's era, as the first Ford Model T was designed to be run on Ethanol. However, gasoline being the cheaper fuel at the time, combined with resistance from Standard Oil (the American Oil Empire consisting of companies like Esso, Chevron, and later British Petroleum), resulted in this movement not gaining full momentum. In 1973, the prices of regular gasoline increased by 57% according to (Stolark, 2016). This paired with routine shortages of the fuel during the same period as well as new regulation of air pollutants paved way for advances in areas like fuel efficiency, electric alternatives, and alternative fuels like Ethanol, which were all previously of low priority. These aforementioned ideas were ways to try and meet the new regulations and reduce dependency on petroleum products. Currently, most pump fuels available in the UK, US, and various other regions consist of a 10% Ethanol blend in their gasoline as a result of this history.

4.5 Gasoline/Ethanol Blends

As (ePure, 2023) explains, Ethanol is the component typically blended with pure petrol/gasoline. Pump fuel in the UK is typically labelled either E5 or E10. This is in regard to the percentage of Ethanol within the blend, with E5 being 95% pure gasoline and 5% Ethanol. (ePure, 2023) explains that E10 has an ever-growing share on the market as the higher Ethanol content in the blend indicates a proven reduction in greenhouse gas emissions when compared to pure gasoline. (North Dakota Commerce, 2023) lists further benefits to using Ethanol as a blend component for gasoline. These benefits include a 2-to-3-point octane boost to regular gasoline depending on the quantity used, providing inherent performance advantages. Another key benefit of Ethanol is that it burns cooler than gasoline, which in turn prevents valve damage. Ethanol also has cleaning properties which keeps the fuel system running optimally and avoids deposit build-up that can hinder engine performance.

4.6 Moving to E85

(eFlexFuel, 2021) outlines what the shift towards E85 means for automotive applications. E85 is a more environmentally friendly fuel when compared to regular gasoline and is the biggest driver towards the shift to either a flex-fuel environment or a purely E85 fuel alternative. The main environmental benefits include a lower carbon footprint and less harmful emissions from combustion. Research from the US Department of Energy's Argonne National Laboratory conducted a study which confirmed that the production of Ethanol from corn crops produced much lower greenhouse gasses when compared to equal volumes of gasoline.

The study indicated that carbon intensity of corn production is ever reducing due to constant improvements in cultivation methods and other advances in production methodology. The latest data shows an approximate 46% reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions when burning E85 compared to the E10 gasoline alternative. This reduction in GHG means a noticeably lower amount of

toxins being released into the atmosphere, this is because E85 does not contain aromatic hydrocarbons that are added to gasoline, which is done to increase the RON of the fuel.

These aromatics are toxic compounds that are not needed in E85 applications as the RON is naturally much higher than gasoline, averaging values of 105 in comparison to 95 RON pump fuel.

Further to the aforementioned environmental benefits, the higher-octane rating of E85 also provides performance benefits when used in automotive applications. As previously mentioned, E85 blends generally have a research octane rating approximately 10 points higher than the most common pump fuel alternatives. With this advantage, engines are theoretically able to perform to higher abilities with the correct supporting modifications before running into detonation or “knock”. This is generally where an engine’s performance becomes limited.

Increased detonation rates are caused by several factors, not limited to: poor quality fuel (i.e. below the target RON level indicated at the pump), running too much boost pressure through methods like turbocharging, supercharging, or pro-charging, as well as running supplementary fuels to help performance in finite quantities such as nitrous oxide to allow for a short burst of power when required. Other factors can also contribute to a more knock-prone engine setup such as running higher compression ratios, lean fuel-burning conditions, as well as very advanced ignition timing settings. All of these contributing factors increase the risk of knock occurring within an engine. The chances are further increased when several of these factors are combined, which can lead to dangerous running conditions with poor life expectancy from the engine.

The risks involved can be reduced by running a higher-octane fuel such as E85 which has increased resistance to detonation. By running this fuel, this allows engineers to take advantage of some of the power adding methods listed above, thus improving engine performance and life-expectancy without reaching detonation levels as quickly, or in some cases at all. In cases of most SI engines, detonation is generally the limiting factor regarding the highest performance an engine can produce. When an ECU is calibrated during a vehicle’s manufacturing process, and in an aftermarket scenario when trying to improve performance, the calibrator will tune the engine by optimising the combustion conditions through the use of a wideband oxygen sensor. This allows the user to see the air-to-fuel ratios (AFRs) after combustion has taken place as the sensor is fitted to a probe in the exhaust piping close to the headers and exhaust valves. This value can be compared to the desired AFRs at any given throttle position, manifold pressure, engine speed, engine load characteristic, as well as any other relevant parameter.

The fuel tables can then be optimised by one of several methods to either increase or decrease the amount of fuel being supplied in that “cell” of the ECU map. After having optimised the AFRs across the fuel table in the Engine Control Unit (ECU), the ignition map can be refined to optimise the spark timing to allow for the best performance possible. This is where knock can be introduced and is a detrimental factor to engine performance and longevity. Ignition tables should always be altered on an engine dyno in order to measure the torque output being produced in real-time.

Having a knock-sensor attached to the engine is a further step needed when looking to optimise ignition timing. With these two pieces of equipment, ignition timing can be increased in the desired increments or degrees BTDC (before top-dead centre). By increasing the ignition advance incrementally, the torque output is read from the dyno and increased until reaching MBT (maximum brake torque) or until detonation is detected. IF MBT is reached safely without any indication of knock, timing is usually locked-in as the best performance is attained. If detonation is detected before MBT is achieved, it is common practice to retard timing further from the detonation point by several degrees to accommodate for poor and inconsistent fuel quality at any time.

The methodology described above is common practice for gasoline engine calibration and differs only slightly when considering E85 or any other blended fuels. The main differences being that MBT is almost always achieved before the engine becomes “knock-limited” as the fuel has a much higher resistance to detonate. The other main area to focus on is the fuelling table, as the Stoichiometric ratio for E85 differs vastly from gasoline, these targets need to be accounted for in the fuel tables. An

important factor to consider is that E85 burns quicker and favours richer burning conditions in comparison to gasoline when it comes to power output. This can be seen when tuning a gasoline engine as MBT is often reached when running under slightly leaner AFR conditions where E85 produces more power under slightly richer conditions. This leads to the next common topic of gasoline versus E85 and other high-Ethanol blends, fuel consumption. As E85 is a gasoline and alcohol blend, a typical vehicle burns 30-40% more fuel on average in order to run at a comparable rate. This equates in an equivalent increase of fuel required to cover the same distance, meaning that the vehicle's fuel economy would decrease proportionally. In countries like the USA and Australia, this can often be justified with the cost of E85 at the pump being significantly lower than comparable gasoline prices. Whereas in the UK, E85 is currently marketed as a race fuel and is not readily available at the pump to-date.

4.7 Running High-Ethanol Fuel Without Vehicle Modifications

As pump fuels can range from 5% Ethanol content all the way up to 85% (E5 to E85) in some countries, it is important to know what is best to run in a vehicle and what the potential benefits and drawbacks associated with running the fuels are. As (Fuel & Friction, 2023) explains, general benefits of running more Ethanol in the vehicle are: increased potential for torque and power output, as well as cooling and cleaning effects due to the increased alcohol percentage. However, they discuss that not all cars are suited to running higher concentrated blends of Ethanol. Older vehicles are not well equipped to run large amounts of Ethanol, this is due to the corrosive nature of Ethanol. It is prone to causing deterioration of Magnesium, Aluminium, and rubber components. This is often rectified by replacing fuel hoses, pumps, seals, gaskets, filters, injectors, and other generally aging components to upgraded parts that are manufactured with materials suited to working with Ethanol.

On top of the hardware requirements mentioned, most vehicles will require an ECU recalibration as explained previously, in order to make use of the chemical benefits that the fuel provides. Recent vehicles manufactured to run "flex-fuel" setups particularly in countries like America, come off the production line with the capability of running any gasoline-Ethanol blend ranging from E5 to E85. This is achieved through utilizing Ethanol content sensors, wideband oxygen sensors, as well as advanced ECU hardware and calibration techniques with transitional map capability. This function is able to interpolate values between fuel and ignition tables according to the percentage of Ethanol that the ECU is reading from the sensor.

Another key drawback to note is that Ethanol is a hygroscopic fuel, meaning that it will absorb moisture from the air when exposed to the elements. This in turn lowers the octane rating of the fuel, thus reducing its performance benefits and shortening the fuels "lifespan". Therefore, the higher the Ethanol content of the blend, the greater the rate of moisture absorption, and in turn the shorter the effective life of the fuel becomes. For this reason, manufacturers recommend that high-Ethanol fuels not be left in a vehicles tank for extended periods and should be filled up and used as necessary to avoid this degradation taking place. Geographical location and weather also play a part in whether E85 and other high Ethanol-based fuels are suitable for a particular vehicle. E85 in particular does not perform at its optimum in cold conditions, this can make cold-starts difficult for engines as well as cause poor idle conditions. Additionally, it can take longer for engines to reach operating temperature, and in turn results in high emissions until the optimal temperature is reached. For the reason explained, many cold regions switch to a "winter blend" when poor weather is expected, meaning that advertised E85 at the pump can often be E50 or lower as the greater gasoline percentage aids in the aforementioned struggles with Ethanol fuels.

4.8 Renewable Gasoline – Reducing Harmful Emissions

As (U.S. Department of Energy, 2023) explains, renewable gasoline is a potential alternative to petroleum-based gasoline. Renewable gasoline can be produced by an array of processes using biomass sources as the raw material. These sources range from lipids (animal fats, greases, algae, and

vegetable oils), as well as cellulosic material (produce crop residues, woody biomass, and dedicated energy crops). Some of the methods used to produce this renewable gasoline are gasification, hydrotreating, and pyrolysis, amongst others. Renewable gasoline produced by these methods is able to be used directly in existing SI combustion engines, as the fuel is chemically identical to that of its fossil-fuel counterpart. Benefits of this sustainable fuel option is the reduced dependency on finite resources such as crude oil, as well as the reduction in the emissions produced. The California Energy Commission confirms a potential 61-83% reduction in carbon dioxide emissions dependant of the feedstock used for the fuel. This provides a viable solution for the generation of gasoline, but leaves room for improvement in terms of harmful emissions released from burning the fuel, as with any other. This is where the introduction of hydrocarbon-free fuels takes interest.

4.9 Hydrocarbon-Free Fuels

Alternative renewable fuels of interest as listed by (U.S. Department of Energy, 2023) are Biobutanol, Methanol, and Ethanol. Whilst Methanol can be produced from the same biomass as used in Ethanol and Biobutanol production, it is most economically produced from natural gas. As the focus is on HC fuels that are derived from renewable sources, the focus is more on Biobutanol and Ethanol. When comparing the two, Biobutanol is immiscible in water. This means that the two substances do not mix easily, this is a key drawback to using Ethanol or E85 blends as Ethanol is hygroscopic and miscible in water. This in turn deteriorates the advantageous properties of the fuel with this effect having a negative result on RON levels and energy density. Similarly with Ethanol, Biobutanol is typically blended with gasoline with a 16% volume share. This compound is a direct equivalent to an E10 pump fuel blend. This blend of fuel meets a 20% reduction in greenhouse gas emission according to the Renewable Fuel Standard. Other key advantages of Biobutanol include a higher energy content when compared with gasoline alternatives, it also has a lower Reid vapour pressure. This means that it is less volatile than Ethanol and produces lower evaporation emissions.

4.10 Spatial Requirements of “Biofuels”

In countries like the USA and Australia where E85 is accessible at the pump in many states, this may be a sensible direction to choose even in the current day. Whereas the UK and other regions still have a long way to go before this is a viable replacement or substitute options. (West, 2021) indicates this to be a result of land availability. As Ethanol requires large areas of land to grow the crops used to produce the fuel, this can take away from the space required to grow crops for human consumption as well as livestock. In parts of the world where land is in abundance and readily available this is less of a concern, compared to smaller countries and particularly Islands with limited room. According to some authorities, producing enough biofuel to allow its widespread adoption could result in the need to convert most of the world’s open spaces and forests into farmland. As this is an unlikely route to be taken, the blend of biofuels and fossil fuels helps reduce the dependency on finite resources whilst still allowing the consumption of fuel at a reduced environmental impact rate.

4.11 Gasoline vs E85 Energy Density

According to (Dsport, 2013), E85 contains roughly 82,000 BTU/Gal whereas E10 pump fuel contains about 110,000 BTU/Gal. This difference in energy density means that E85 contains roughly 75% of the energy of E10 per unit volume. This translates to a higher volume of E85 fuel required in order to meet comparable targets as when running E10. In order to compensate for this gap in energy density, cars running on E85 generally demand a 35-40% increase in fuel supply volume as compared to the same engine running on pump fuel. As a result of this, driving fuel economy is reduced. For example, if a vehicle typically averages 200km on a 50L tank of pump fuel, switching to E85 will mean an expected 150km range on the same 50L volume of fuel. What this means is that manufacturers and vehicle owners will need to ensure that their fuel system is capable of providing the required volume of fuel

without the need to upgrade components in order to run E85. Typical components to be considered are; fuel pumps, fuel injectors, pressure regulators, and fuel lines. The components therefore need to be able to flow a greater volume of fuel at equal or greater pressure.

5. Simulation

5.1 Software Simulation Package

Ricardo's WAVE software package, as (Realis, n.d.) explains, is a 1-Dimensional gas dynamics simulation tool, which enables performance and acoustic analyses to be performed for any intake, combustion, and exhaust system configuration. This can be applied to any industry such as ground transport, rail, marine, power generation, or motor sport. WAVE simulation software solves 1-D Navier-Stokes equations governing the transfer of mass, momentum, and energy for compressible gas flows, and includes sub-models for combustion and emissions.

For the purpose of this investigation, the 2.0 Ford Zetec engine was replicated. This engine is an ideal contender for this experiment as it is a conventional SI engine found in many cars in the Ford fleet, ranging from small hatchbacks to people-carriers and everything in-between. As such, it is a commonly found engine on the roads today and has been since its' release back in 1991, according to (TorqueCars, 2000). The engine parameters were replicated as closely as possible within the Ricardo WAVE software through a combination of workshop-based measurements, engine specification data sheets, as well as further estimations and simplifications made by the software in terms of ideal fuelling and running conditions.

Due to some of the estimations made by the simulation software, results may vary when compared to real-world test cases. As a prime example of simulation variation, the WAVE software assumes a perfect identical burn cycle between all cylinders and in all conditions. For this reason, scenarios like heat-soak during engine dyno-testing is not able to be replicated in the simulations. This condition can have a significant effect on engine performance in the real-world. Another key consideration to be made is that there is no variation between burns within the software testing. This is not always the case when considering a real engine as the slightest change in variables like fuel pressure, fuel quality, air temperature, and impurities within the combustion chamber can vary in every engine cycle, where the software assumes uniformity every time. Whilst these may seem like small variations and may well be omitted from consideration in some test scenarios, they are worth considering for this simulation case. The combination of multiple error forms listed above will also contribute to the greater overall error being relayed through test results.

Whilst the exact torque and power curves vary slightly between the simulation and test data, the area of interest lies within the trends that are shown by the data. These are used as a comparison between simulation results and real-world test results.

As mentioned above, there are variables that cannot be controlled or replicated in the software to mimic the real conditions, as there are real-world conditions that cannot be controlled or replicated for every dyno test run. The trends, patterns, and overall conclusions made by the results, however, are of key interest for this study.

The figures below depict the engine layout as a replica of the 2.0 Ford Zetec engine within the software, using critical information such as: engine bore and stroke dimensions, valve stem and seat dimensions, cam lift and duration profiles, and intake and exhaust duct lengths and diameters. Wall thicknesses of piping, fuel injector location, catalytic converter restriction size, engine compression ratios, fuel characteristic profiles, and simulated running conditions like intake temperatures, throttle valve opening positions, and user defined engine speed run cases are also set up within the software.

5.2 WAVE Engine Model

Figure 3 - Full Engine Model Representation in WAVE - (Author, 2023)

Figure 4 - Highlighted Intake Runner Section - (Author, 2023)

Figure 5 - Highlighted Exhaust Manifold Section - (Author, 2023)

Figure 6 - Indicated Catalytic Converter and Exhaust Section - (Author, 2023)

Figure 7 - Imported Exhaust Muffler Model - (Author, 2023)

Figure 3 shown above illustrates the full engine model within the WAVE software. With the red highlighted components showing key engine parts such as the intake trumpets, intake runners, throttle bodies, injectors, intake manifold, and intake valves in figure 4. The exhaust valves and manifold section of the exhaust are found in figure 5, with the catalytic converter (restrictive airflow representation), muffler, and exhaust tip seen in figures 6 and 7.

As simulation testing was carried out in parallel with the engine testing, test conditions were replicated like-for-like wherever possible. Initially, an intake runner parametric study was carried out on the simulation engine as discussed below. After obtaining satisfactory results from this experiment, further testing was carried out in both simulation and real-world testing environments. Once testing on the dynamometer commenced, it was apparent that there were some challenges in the way of throttle control as well as what dynamic test limits the dyno would allow. Due to this learning, the conditions were replicated in the WAVE model, particularly regarding the maximum engine speed as well as throttle opening conditions, this is discussed in detail in the 'Testing' section below.

5.3 WAVE Input Data

Table 1 below shows the required input data used to replicate the 2.0 Zetec engine within the Ricardo WAVE simulation environment. Figure 8 shows the calculation for Stoichiometric Oxygen to Fuel Ratio of pure gasoline which is a key consideration for the WAVE software.

Using the Global Equation: $C_m H_n + 2(O_2) \rightarrow 2H_2O + CO_2$

Where:

- m and n are determined by the hydrocarbons in question (with C_8H_{18} being gasoline)
- The assumed volume of Oxygen in air 23.2%.

The figure below shows the calculated Oxygen-to-Fuel Ratio of Gasoline:

The screenshot shows a software interface titled 'TOOLBOX' with a copyright notice 'M A Saunders © 22/04/2023'. It features a 'Fundamental Equation' section with the general reaction: $C_x H_y + a O_2 \rightarrow v_1 CO_2 + v_2 H_2O$. Input fields for 'Enter x' (8) and 'Enter y' (18) are present. Below this, three balance equations are shown: Carbon Balance (8 = v₁), Hydrogen Balance (18 = 2 × v₂), and Oxygen Balance (2 × a = (2 × v₁) + (v₂)). The resulting balanced equation is $2 (C_8 H_{18}) + 25 O_2 \rightarrow 16 C O_2 + 18 H_2 O$. To the right, the 'Oxygen : Fuel Ratio' is displayed as 3.51 : 1. At the bottom, mass calculations are shown: 228 + 800 = 1028 and 704 + 324 = 1028. There are also buttons for 'OK' and 'Use Multiplier' (set to 2).

Figure 8 – Toolbox showing Oxygen-to-Fuel Calculation for pure Gasoline - (Author, 2023)

In order to calculate the Air-to-Fuel Ratio for gasoline from this, the following calculations are made:

$$AFR = \frac{\text{Mass of Oxygen Required} * 100}{\% \text{ Vol of Oxygen in Air}}$$

Therefore:

$$AFR = \frac{3.51 * 100}{23.2} = 15.1$$

This means that in order to completely burn 1 part of fuel, 15.1 parts of air is required. As pump gasoline is typically known to have a Stoichiometric Ratio of around 14.7:1, this is to account for impurities and blends within in the fuel. As an example, pump fuel is typically 5-20% Ethanol rather than 100% pure gasoline.

Table 1 - Table Showing Ford Zetec Engine Specifications - (Author, 2023)

2.0 Ford Zetec Engine Specifications	
Engine Configuration	Inline Four, 4-Stroke
Engine Displacement	1991 cc
Engine Firing Order	1-3-4-2
Engine Cooling	Liquid
Compression Ratio	9.6: 1
Valves Per Cylinder	4
Intake Valves Per Cylinder	2
Exhaust Valves Per Cylinder	2
Bore x Stroke	85 mm x 88 mm
Connecting Rod Length	150 mm
Measured Peak Horsepower	95.5 kW
Measured Peak Torque	178 Nm
Engine Redline	6,750 RPM
Intake Valve Diameter	32 mm
Exhaust Valve Diameter	28 mm
Intake Valve Maximum Lift	9.90 mm
Exhaust Valve Maximum Lift	9.35 mm
Exhaust System Type	Tubular 4-1 Manifold
Throttle Body Venturi Size	45 mm
Valve Timing	
Intake Valve Open BTDC	27 Degrees
Duration	280 Degrees
Exhaust Valve Open BTDC	69 Degrees
Duration	272 Degrees

For the second phase of testing, the stoichiometric ratio for E85 fuel was required as an input for WAVE software as well as for the engine ECU. The figure below by (Diaz, 2023) shows the ideal AFR for E85 to be 9.75. This value is typically rounded up to 9.8 for simplification reasons as inputs are often limited to 1 decimal place.

The screenshot shows a software interface with the following fields and values:

- Select a fuel:** Fuel type dropdown menu set to **Ethanol E85**.
- Air-fuel ratio (AFR):** Input field showing **9.75 :1**.
- Mass of air and fuel:**
 - Mass of fuel:** Input field showing **1 kg**.
 - Mass of air:** Input field showing **9.75 kg**.

Figure 9 - E85 Stoichiometric Air-to-Fuel Ratio - (Diaz, 2023)

5.4 Engine Parametric Study using Pump Fuel (Wide-Open Throttle)

As the initial torque and power output results differ when compared to the engine dyno test data, a parametric study was conducted on the model which involved varying the lengths of the intake runners to observe how it affected the torque and power curves. Theoretically, this should only change the engine speed at which peak torque and power is achieved. However, the trends shown, and peak values should be within comparable range. The parametric study consisted of 6 further iterations excluding the original runner length, where the overall intake runner lengths were varied by 10mm at a time, both shorter and longer than the original measured length from the test engine. The results of the study are shown in the graphs below:

Figure 10 - Torque Output Graph for Parametric Study - (Author, 2023)

Figure 11 - Power Output Graph for Parametric Study - (Author, 2023)

The parametric study shown above was run using “Indolene” fuel within WAVE which is characteristic of regular pump gasoline. This test was run at the initial ideal max engine speed of 7,000 RPM which was later discovered to be outside of the possible scope for the engine dyno test runs. For the purposes of the test, all other parameters remained constant between runs apart from the overall intake runner lengths, which were shortened or lengthened according to the test. The study confirms that varying the length slightly shifts the peak torque value and peak point on the RPM scale, without having a significant impact on the peak values themselves. As shown particularly in the torque output graph, the longest intake runner (purple line) shows the best overall performance with the shallowest troughs, the least amount of torque “spikes”, as well as the highest overall torque output. Whilst this study was useful in confirming the theory behind the effects of intake runner length variation, as well providing assurance that the power and torque output curves were realistic. The decision was made to continue further simulations with the original runner lengths of 55mm (black line) for further testing. This was decided as the results show that the intake lengths have minimal impact on this particular case-study, and that results from the original length of 55mm produced realistic results for further testing. For the purposes of this study, 100% throttle plate angle was used for the best result accuracy and consistency.

5.5 E10 WAVE Simulations

E10 Pump Fuel WAVE Engine Simulations at Varied Throttle Openings (7,000RPM Limit)

The following figures show results obtained from running the replica Ford engine within the WAVE software at varied throttle position openings, in order to replicate the test results from the dyno runs in the “Testing” section below. The settings chosen for the simulated throttle plate openings was dictated by the capability of the engine dyno. As was only discovered during engine testing, the Dynostar eddy current engine dynamometer that was used for practical testing has low-resolution throttle control. This means that the increments of throttle opening are large and inconsistent (meaning that increments between throttle positions may not be equally separated, e.g., 20% throttle to 35% throttle to 40% throttle rather than in steady increments of 10%). There was limited control for the user during this testing, and therefore the real-world settings have been replicated in order to retain some consistency between software simulation and dynamometer results wherever possible. The results for the initial E10 test runs (before introducing the new engine speed limit) are shown in the 2 figures below:

Figure 12 - Torque Output for E10 Pump Fuel at 7,000 RPM - (Author, 2023)

Figure 13 - Power Output for E10 Pump Fuel at 7,000 RPM - (Author, 2023)

E10 Pump Fuel WAVE Engine Simulations at Varied Throttle Openings (4,000RPM Limit)

As governed by the limitations of the engine dyno software, the throttle opening increments for this study during the first session of E10 testing are as follows; 20%, 35%, 40%, and 60%. This in turn translates to the percentage angle associated with the throttle plate butterfly, meaning at 0% throttle the butterfly valve is set to 0 degrees. At the other end of the scale, 100% throttle operation is where the valve is set to 90 degrees. Therefore, the translation from throttle percentage to butterfly valve angle for the purpose of this run case are: 18, 31.5, 36, and 54 degrees respectively.

For the purposes of retaining consistent results between dyno testing and software simulation, engine RPM limitations were also adhered to as explained thoroughly in the Testing section below. As outlined, engine speed during engine testing was limited to a maximum of 4,000 RPM for health & safety reasons as well as those of engine and dynamometer preservation. So, in order to retain uniformity throughout the study, the maximum engine speed for simulation run cases was also limited to 4,000 RPM.

The graphs below indicate the torque and power output values observed through software simulations when adhering to the engine speed and throttle position limitations outlined earlier. An additional run case of 100% throttle opening at the limited RPM was also carried out in order to observe any potential differences in torque and power output even though this particular case could not be achieved on the engine dyno.

Figure 14 - Torque Output for E10 Pump Fuel at 4,000 RPM - (Author, 2023)

Figure 15 - Power Output for E10 Pump Fuel at 4,000 RPM - (Author, 2023)

As the results of these simulations show, there is a direct correlation between the torque and power output with relation to the amount of throttle being applied. Each increased step in throttle clearly indicates a significant rise in peak torque and power values gained. There is however, very minimal variation in both power and torque curves from 1,000 RPM to approximately 2,500 RPM for all throttle positions greater than 20%. This is likely due to the engine already operating at its greatest efficiency, without the provision of increased air and fuel being of great advantage before the 2,500 RPM point.

After this speed, the curves start to diverge more noticeably, with the trends continuing to follow the expectations of a higher throttle opening yielding better performance. This is noticed until the comparison between 60% and 100% throttle cases are compared. As the graphs both show, there is only slight variation between the curves for both power and torque. It is possible that these run cases do not give the full picture as the end of the data shows a difference in the angle that the paths are following, as the curves for the 60% throttle opening appear to start to taper off around the 4,000 RPM region, following suit of the 20-40% run cases. The power and torque curves for 100% throttle opening seem to be angled higher, indicating that peak values for power and torque may not have been achieved yet. For this reason, an extended run case was investigated in order to conclude whether this assumption was true, the 100% throttle opening case was extended from 4,000 to 7,000 RPM as shown in the section below.

E10 Pump Fuel Performance Simulation Results at Realistic Engine Redline (100% Throttle Opening)

According to (Zal, 2010), the Zetec engine typically has an engine redline of between 6,500 and 7,000 RPM. To test how this affects torque and power curves compared to being limited by the capabilities of testing with the engine dynamometer, a simulation was carried out with all the same variables as tested with the throttle openings shown in cases above, however using the more realistic engine rev limit of 7,000 RPM. For the purposes of comparison without hardware limitations as shown above, indolene fuel was simulated at 100% throttle (90-degree butterfly valve opening) and the results shown in the figures below:

Figure 16 - Engine Torque Output at W.O.T with E10 Fuel (7,000 RPM) - (Author, 2023)

Figure 17 - Engine Power Output at W.O.T with E10 Fuel (7,000 RPM) - (Author, 2023)

As earlier hypothesised, the engine was able to continue producing torque and power well past the 4,000 RPM section initially investigated. As this run case was not possible to be confirmed on the engine dyno, the results of this case were used purely to justify the close results gained from the 60% and 100% torque and power curves gained during the 4,000 RPM test cases.

5.6 E85 WAVE Simulations

E85 Fuel WAVE Engine Simulations at Varied Throttle Openings (Original Air-Fuel Ratios)

As mentioned previously with the pump fuel dyno testing, the throttle valve opening positions were dictated by what the dynamometer system allowed at the time. During the session of E85 fuel testing, the dynamometer throttle openings allowed by the Dynostar varied slightly to the throttle openings allowed previously during the E10 testing session. The simulation settings have in turn been modified to match as closely as possible, and the results are shown below. Originally testing with un-altered air-fuel ratios (using a target stoichiometric value of 14.7: 1), the throttle openings used were 30% and 100%. These tests were run to observe the outcome of attempting to run an “un-modified” engine on E85 fuel without altering any of the fuel parameters in the engine ECU software. The results of this initial investigation are shown in the graphs below.

Figure 18 - E85 Torque Output using Gasoline AFRs - (Author, 2023)

Figure 19 - E85 Power Output using Gasoline AFRs - (Author, 2023)

E85 Fuel WAVE Engine Simulations (Using Ideal Target Air-Fuel Ratios)

For the cases replicating the engine dyno tests, the target air-fuel ratio was set closer to stoichiometric value for E85 of 9.81: 1. The throttle positions used were as allowed by the engine dyno again, being: 30%, 40%, 60%, 70%, 75%, 85%, 95%, and 100%. The results for both torque and power achieved using E85 with the appropriate modifications are as shown in the figures below.

Figure 204 - E85 Torque Output using E85 AFRs - (Author, 2023)

Figure 21 - E85 Power Output using E85 AFRs - (Author, 2023)

Similarly, as found with the 4,000 RPM run cases for E10/Indolene in the original test, the results of the E85 simulations follow the same patterns. This is to be expected as the engine model, engine speed, throttle openings, and all other relevant parameters remain uniform with the E10 test cases. The key differences being the fuel model used within the WAVE software, and the target air-fuel ratio being suited to E85 rather than E10 gasoline. The results are similar in the sense that torque and power output values are quite close between all throttle openings from 30% to 100% from 1,000 RPM to approximately 2,000 RPM. In this instance, throttle positions greater than 40% through to 100% have similar performance values, all of which appear to still be climbing at the 4,000 RPM cut-off point of the graphs. Peak torque observed at throttle openings above 60% with E85 appear to be 143Nm and 148Nm at 4,000 RPM whereas peak torque for E10 at the same engine speed fell between 141Nm and 143Nm for 60% and 100% throttle respectively. As the peak power figures gained for both fuel types differed marginally, the initial conclusion drawn from the results thus far is that E85 was able to obtain marginally greater torque performance, with minimal gains in power output. For this reason, a subsidiary test was carried out in order to observe the outcome of a 100% throttle test using E85 fuel and allowing the engine to speed up to 7,000 RPM as with the Indolene test case.

The graphs below show the results of this case study and are compared with the relevant E10 test results above.

Figure 22 - Engine Power Output at W.O.T with E85 Fuel (7,000 RPM) - (Author, 2023)

Figure 23 - Engine Power Output at W.O.T with E85 Fuel (7,000 RPM) - (Author, 2023)

As the compiled data from this final simulation shows, E85 fuel yields a greater performance output under ideal burn conditions. This is initially determined as a marginally higher torque output is observed with this fuel. E85 has produced an approximate peak torque value of 172Nm whereas E10 pump fuel indicated a value closer to 167Nm. Peak torque is also observed at roughly 5,050 RPM on E85 fuel whereas peak torque is seen at 5,500 RPM on E10 fuel. Further to this, peak power of the engine is noted around 110kW for both types of fuel. Whilst alone there is no performance benefit by using E85, the point at which peak power is observed is approximately 500 RPM earlier by using this fuel. This is beneficial in its own right when discussing vehicle performance.

6. Testing

6.1 Engine Testing Equipment

In order to conduct a comparative study between simulated software estimations and real-world test results, engine performance testing was carried out using a 2.0L Ford Zetec engine on a test bed paired with a DynoStar ETB500 Eddy Current Dynamometer. The DynoStar ETB500 equipment is education-based with limitations on its capabilities but is fit for demonstration purposes as well as being suitable for carrying out the majority of requirements needed to run the experiment as shown below.

As (Dynamometers.org, 2023) explains, an eddy current dynamometer is an electromechanical energy conversion device that converts mechanical energy into electrical energy. It works by inducing an EMF on a set of conductors that is a result of relative displacement between the conductor and a magnetic field. This dynamically induced EMF is a result of Faraday's Law of Electromagnetic Induction. The EMF is then able to be controlled through the use of the dyno software in order to achieve two key outcomes. The first is being able to control the speed and load applied on the engine through the use of applying an electromagnetic "brake". The second is the ability to determine the engine speed and torque output of the engine. These values are then used further in calculations to determine the power output of the engine.

Dynostar (n.d.) lists the dynamometer limitations as a maximum engine running speed of 7,000 RPM, as well as maximum engine power capability of 125kW (at continuous load), 165kW (at a maximum run time of 3 minutes), and 275kW (maximum power handling capacity when equipment is cold).

The 2.0 test engine is said to produce approximately 128BHP according to Parkers (2023), which translates to 95kW. Calculated by taking the original BHP value and dividing it by 1.341. This shows that the engine power output is well within the capability of the dyno's measurement and eddy current braking range.

The DAS (Data Acquisition System) software that is provided with the engine dyno is capable of monitoring various critical parameters within the engine operating environment. The most important being engine power output (in kW), torque output (in Nm), Air-to-Fuel Ratio post-burn, throttle actuator position, and coolant temperature. This functionality is critical from the data collection perspective as the dyno software is responsible for communicating back and forth between the dynamometer and computer in order to deliver the output parameters required by the study, namely being engine torque and power output versus engine speed. Any other data retrieval and engine control is done via the engine's ECU software. This in turn handles input parameters that the calibrator defines, as well as output data that the ECU reads from engine sensors such as temperatures, pressures, and throttle input amongst others, dependant on the particular engine. This particular Zetec engine has been modified to run using a Megasquirt ECU rather than the OEM (Original Equipment Manufacturer) factory unit, as this aftermarket ECU provides more capability to customise and fine-tune setups according to the purpose of the engine. It is also a more accessible and user-friendly software package to use (TunerStudio). The OEM provided ECU for this engine is locked from the factory, meaning that parameters cannot be modified and thus would not be suitable for this investigation nor any others involving the need to adjust fuel and ignition timing requirements.

TunerStudio software allows for the user to change input parameters such as target AFRs, fuel tables and ignition maps. The MegaSquirt ECU is also able to read data from engine sensors such as throttle position, engine speed (via crank angle sensor), exhaust temperature, coolant temperature, fuelling and ignition trims (corrections), manifold air pressure, intake air temperature, as well as provisions to add additional sensors at a later date to further improve control. Some key sensors that would be particularly beneficial in this circumstance are wideband oxygen sensor feedback, as well as knock

detection. As this setup is currently missing these two vital sensors, there are some apparent limitations when it comes to modifying the fuelling tables and ignition timing of this engine. This comes from a safety perspective as well as a performance standpoint. The details of the limits are further discussed below, but as an overview, spark ignition timing advance and lean running conditions are limited as the ECU and calibrator are not able to detect when the engine is experiencing detonation. Due to this factor, the ignition timing settings chosen are conservative and may not be reaching the full potential of the engine as the ECU cannot detect the dangerous running condition and therefore cannot implement safety features. These features involve temporarily retarding ignition timing and/or increasing fuelling to avoid damage. Further to this point, not having wideband oxygen or “lambda” sensor feedback into the ECU means that the engine dyno oxygen sensor can read the AFR at the tailpipe but is not able to relay this information back to the ECU. Thus, making it impossible for the ECU to make corrections to fuelling and ignition, much like the case with the lack of knock sensor feedback. For this reason, AFRs can be read live during testing but cannot be recorded or fed back into the ECU software. This again makes for limited tuning ability, as the target AFR tables programmed into the ECU are not able to be utilised (as seen in Appendix 8).

Disclaimer: Due to reasons mentioned in the section above, testing and manipulation of parameters within the engine ECU are limited within reason. Due to the lack of knock feedback paired with the need to preserve the University’s asset, ignition timing manipulation was limited in order to remain within the safe operating region of the engine. Hence, the results may not be true in representing the maximum possible performance from the engine under both gasoline and E85 running conditions. Secondly to this reason, the close proximity of the engine and dynamometer cell to the users and other students in the workshop environment meant that test runs were limited to approximately 4,000 RPM. This was added insurance to minimise the dangers to people surrounding the area as well as to preserve the University asset for future use. Test results may vary under ideal testing conditions.

An example of the dyno data displayed after a test run is shown in the figure below. Torque and power curves are displayed on a single graph. Data is then exported in raw form and converted into a notepad document. It is then finally imported into Microsoft Excel as a comma de-limited file in order to tabulate the raw data and finally produce the graphs shown in other figures within this document.

Figure 24 - Dyno Graph Sample from ET500 Equipment - (Author, 2023)

6.2 E10 Pump Fuel Testing

Pump Fuel Engine Dynamometer Results at Varied Throttle Openings (4,000RPM Limit)

The graphs below are representative of the initial test session with the engine dynamometer. The tests were carried out using E10 pump gasoline sourced from a local petrol station. As mentioned earlier, the dyno constraints of this session were that the throttle openings allowed were between 20% and 60%. For unknown reasons, the engine dyno would not allow throttle increments in-between the values tested for below. The dyno also did not allow any tests at throttle openings of more than 60%. When this was attempted, the engine experienced symptoms similar to diesel engine “runaway”. This is common in diesel (compression ignition) engines where the engine speeds up out of control due to an auxiliary fuel source being burned unintentionally, such as a turbo oil leak. However, in the case of this testing session, the runaway was caused by the dynamometer not applying adequate load to the engine in order to control the RPM, instead it would free-rev up to dangerously high speeds. The run cases at these times were aborted due to the high risk of damaging the engine beyond repair. As it appeared that running the engine at 100% throttle was outside the capabilities of the dyno at this time, the decision was made to limit the test runs to a throttle opening that proved safe for the users and equipment. The results of the test cases following this are shown in the figures below.

Figure 25 - Torque Output for E10 Pump Fuel at 4,000 RPM - (Author, 2023)

Figure 26 - Power Output for E10 Pump Fuel at 4,000 RPM - (Author, 2023)

As the test data indicates, similarly to the results of the WAVE simulations, the increase in throttle plate opening allows for greater performance in both torque and power output. Again, when comparing test data to simulation data, it is apparent that the curves follow a similar trend to one another regardless of throttle position. The key difference noted when comparing the two data sets is that the gaps between data trends are more apparent on the test engine whereas the curves followed a close path until 2-3,000 RPM where they diverged more obviously with the WAVE simulations. The next key area of interest when comparing simulation results to physical test results is the peak performance values yielded in both power and torque output. Whilst the peak power output at 60% throttle of the test engine came in at approximately 43kW, the WAVE model yielded peak power of approximately 58kW. On the contrary however, the peak torque values were closer as observed by the engine producing 135Nm, and the peak value indicated from the simulation being 142Nm. Whilst being within a close range of results from one another, the key notable difference between simulation results and test engine findings are to do with the shape of the path and therefore the point at which the peak values are observed. For the power output cases, the trend is similar as peak output is towards the higher engine speeds, and still climbing in the case of both 60% throttle instances. The torque curves however indicate dissimilar patterns with peak torque for the physical engine being indicated at approximately 2,250 RPM, with peak torque of the simulated version being closer to 4,000 RPM with the indication of possible increase with higher engine speed being permitted.

6.3 E85 Ethanol-Blend Fuel Testing

E85 Fuel Engine Dynamometer Results at Varied Throttle Openings (4,000RPM Limit) – Iteration 1

With the awareness of the dynamometer’s capabilities and restrictions after the E10 gasoline testing, the E85 fuel testing session was prepared. After calibrating the engine dyno in readiness for the testing as done previously, extra steps were required in order to run the E85 fuel without causing damage to the engine. In order to allow the conventional Ford engine to run on E85, the volume of fuel being fed into the intake manifold was modified. As calculated at the start of the Testing section, it was apparent that switching from E10 to E85 would require approximately a 40% fuel increase in order to achieve similar lambda values for ideal burn conditions, irrespective of the particular air-fuel ratios required. With a lambda value of 1 being complete combustion of the fuel. Anything below lambda 1 indicates a rich burning condition, contrary to any value above lambda 1 indicating a lean-burn condition. To achieve this, the MegaSquirt ECU was accessed through TunerStudio. The main reason for this was to alter the Volumetric Efficiency table. This is what the ECU uses as a reference to determine how much fuel should be supplied to the engine at any given engine speed and throttle position. For the first phase of testing, the entire volumetric efficiency table was modified to allow for a 40% fuel increase (as seen in Appendix 4 and 6). This adjustment “tricks” the ECU into thinking that the engine is more efficient than it is and therefore supplies more fuel as it believes there is a greater charge of air being drawn in due to this “increased efficiency”. The engine was then tested without any further changes, and at the allowed throttle settings as shown in the graphs below.

Figure 27 - Torque Output for E85 Pump Fuel at 4,000 RPM (1st Iteration) - (Author, 2023)

E85 Fuel - Power vs Engine Speed - 1st Iteration (4k RPM)

Figure 28 - Power Output for E85 Pump Fuel at 4,000 RPM (1st Iteration) - (Author, 2023)

As the graphs show, there were some inconsistencies during the first phase of testing. Initially, the graphs indicate data missing from 500 RPM to 1,000 RPM for all run cases apart from 30,40, and 65% throttle. As the dyno was set to record data from 500 RPM, a technical error from the dyno software was the cause of the gaps in the data, albeit relatively unimportant for the purposes of maximum performance studies. The next most prominent anomaly noted on the graphs is the pink curve belonging to 100% throttle actuation. This line does not follow the trend shown by all other run cases and is due to the engine running lean during this power run, this was simply due to the fuel tank running low, causing the fuel pump to be unable to supply enough fuel at the required pressure. As previously mentioned, AFR readings were not able to be recorded, which would have indicated the exact areas of the fuel table that needed further enrichment or leaning of the air-fuel mixture. As this was not possible, the AFRs were monitored during a live sweep test in order to estimate the areas of the map that required adjustment.

The second iteration of the E85 testing procedure commenced after re-fuelling of the engine was complete. During this ECU re-calibration the volumetric efficiency (VE) table was further modified according to the results of the AFR readings produced during the first session of testing. Second to this method of adjustment, the engine was held running at particular cells within the fuel map table by running the dyno in steady state. This meant that the engine was kept at a certain RPM with a fixed throttle opening and was able to be adjusted in real-time whilst the output values for AFR, torque, and power were being read off the dyno software. The combination of these methods aided in adjusting the volumetric efficiency tables to achieve the ideal AFR reading, as well as monitoring the performance of the engine during the changes. After having completed the VE adjustments, the ignition timing advance table was adjusted (as shown in Appendix 5 and 7) using the same monitoring techniques as with the VE tables, keeping in mind that the lack of detonation feedback limited the extent of the ignition advance being applied. This meant that even in cases where MBT may not have been achieved, the ignition-advance never exceeded 4 degrees greater than the original value in the table. This was done with intent to prevent any damage to the engine as well as the protect the wellbeing of any persons in the vicinity of the dyno cell. The results of the second iteration are shown below, again with the throttle openings determined by the allowance of the engine dyno.

E85 Fuel Engine Dynamometer Results at Varied Throttle Openings (4,000RPM Limit) – Iteration 2

Figure 29 - Torque Output for E85 Pump Fuel at 4,000 RPM (2nd Iteration) - (Author, 2023)

Figure 30 - Power Output for E85 Pump Fuel at 4,000 RPM (2nd Iteration) - (Author, 2023)

From the results of the second E85 testing session, the fuel and ignition parameters were modified further. With AFRs closer to target stoichiometric ratios, the engine calibration was further enhanced. The results of this enhancement combined with the ignition timing alterations indicate a performance gain as shown in the graphs above.

Focusing initially on the anomalies shown in the torque and power graphs, the trends of all but the 70% run show gaps in the indicated data at low engine speed. Similarly with the 1st iteration of E85 testing, where the engine dyno failed to record data from 500 RPM. This was the case with the second session of testing with the 70% throttle run being the exception. Secondly, the curves for 30% and 50% throttle openings appear to have data missing from higher engine speeds as well. This is indicated as the data curves terminate at approximately 3,250 and 3,000 RPM for 30% and 50% respectively. The reason for this is that the engine would not accelerate passed these speeds with the respective throttle plate opening angles. This was later discovered to be a result of lean running conditions in these areas of the fuel map, as well as retarded ignition timing. As it was not possible to reach the required data cells to adjust these conditions in the ECU software on this dyno, the data points were disregarding during comparison studies. Another key factor in deciding to omit the results of low throttle plate openings is because high-performance conditions are more relative to more demanding engine speeds which typically occur at WOT or thereabouts. The difficult-to-reach cells in question can be seen circled in appendix [2] and [3].

7. E10 vs E85 Performance Comparisons

As the simulation and testing sections above indicate, there are clear results for both methodologies investigated. Contrary to the facts and expectations outlined from the literature study, the greatest engine performance output was yielded from running conventional pump gasoline in real-world case studies, however E85 slightly out-performed pump fuel in a software simulation environment. E85 fuel test results indicated a lower peak performance of both torque and power output in dyno testing, this is found on numerous occasions through various engine conditions, including low and high engine speeds as well as at any throttle position from 30% right through to wide-open throttle.

As determined by the decisions made during the final testing stage of E85, limitations with the dyno's ability to focus on particular cells made fine-tuning difficult/impossible in particular areas. For this reason, it was decided that the key areas for comparison would focus on higher throttle position opening when comparing both E10 and E85 fuel results. This was also the case when comparing simulations results and testing results for both fuels. The figures below overlay power and torque results from both fuel types as well as both methods of testing, all within one graph in order to clearly identify conclusive results. Ignition timing and volumetric efficiency tables for E10 and E85 fuels within the MegaSquirt ECU can be found in appendix [4]-[7] for comparison purposes.

The torque results of the comparison study can be found in the figures below:

Figure 31 - Engine Torque Comparison (40% Throttle) - (Author, 2023)

Figure 32 - Engine Torque Comparison (60% Throttle) - (Author, 2023)

Figure 33 - Engine Torque Comparison (100% Throttle) - (Author, 2023)

Using figures 31 and 32 as evidence, the result of the testing indicates that E10 has out-performed E85 during real-world testing, but the contrary has taken place during simulation-based studies. This is indicated by the greater torque output gained from E10 fuel which is shown by the red lines on the graphs, when compared to the green E85 curve. There is a greater gap observed in performance during physical testing when compared to the marginal variation between fuel performance in the WAVE-based environment. When considering all results regardless of the source, E85 provided the best torque performance overall as indicated by figures 31-33. This result indicates that there is potential for this statement to be true within the practical testing environment as well with further work being carried out. Whilst only indicating a marginal improvement when running E85 over E10, WAVE has indicated a definite performance benefit which may in turn be further developed within the model to extract larger performance gains.

The power output results of the comparison study can be found in the figures below:

Figure 34 - Engine Power Comparison (40% Throttle) - (Author, 2023)

Figure 35- Engine Power Comparison (60% Throttle) - (Author, 2023)

Figure 36 - Engine Power Comparison (100% Throttle) - (Author, 2023)

As the data in figures 34 and 35 indicates, the results of the power output produced by the engine coincide with that of the torque output data above. As expected, the results of power generated follow suit with what was explained in the section discussing torque output comparisons. To elaborate further on the points made above, (HP Academy, 2023) explains that to make the most out of using E85 or any high-Ethanol fuel, the engine must be knock-limited when running on regular pump fuel. This is where a naturally aspirated engine is unable to make use of more advanced ignition timing due to detonation limitations being reached before arriving at MBT. If the engine is already reaching MBT without detonation, running E85 will have minimal benefits in terms of power output alone. This may be in cases where low-compression engine design is used. In order to take full advantage of running E85, revisions need to be made at a design level where higher compression is used, as well as the introduction of forced induction. This can be in the form of turbocharging or supercharging the engine, which in turn creates more heat in the combustion chamber and introduces knock limitations. With the forced induction mechanisms in place, E85 can then be used for more densely charged air mixtures. This in turn results in greater performance output without the risk of knock-limitations.

An example of this knock-resistance characteristic being utilised is shown in Figure 37 below. This image shows the results from a high-compression turbocharged engine in a Subaru Impreza being dyno tested on E10 pump fuel, and then re-calibrated to take advantage of the benefits of E85. The results clearly show an increase in performance right across the spectrum regarding all engine speeds as well as a considerable improvement in both torque and power output.

Figure 37 – Turbocharged Subaru Impreza E10 vs E85 Performance Comparison - (JM Automotive, 2023)

8. Conclusion

To conclude the study, the results of testing have shown that whilst the E10 parameters currently outperform E85 on the engine dyno, there is the potential for the capabilities of E85 to be utilised as indicated in the WAVE testing results as well as the forced-induction results shown by (JM Automotive, 2023). Currently, the performance gains indicated by the WAVE simulations are marginal, as they do currently yield better peak torque and power figures, and in some cases have proved to bring in peak torque earlier in the RPM range. This is beneficial in both street driving conditions as well as in motorsport. Early arrival of peak torque means that engines do not need to work as hard to produce the torque demanded by the driver. This in turn has mechanical benefits as valvetrain components and rotating assemblies are under less strain during operation.

There are considerations to be made regarding the margin for error when carrying out this investigation. Firstly, when considering the WAVE simulation section, the software makes some assumptions that are done in order to simplify the calculation processes and give consistent results. However, these assumptions and simplifications do not apply during real-world testing. This variable between software study versus practical testing creates errors that are worth considering, namely being cycle-by-cycle variations that take place within the running of a physical engine. These errors are eliminated by the software, as it simulates an ideal, identical operating cycle, which is not possible in the real world. Secondly, WAVE simulations follow a set of fixed values for variables such as intake temperatures, combustion temperatures, heat transfer patterns, and so on, which can be measured in a practical environment to an extent but are not perfectly consistent. These imperfections in minor variables add up over the duration of a study and have the potential to alter findings by a considerable margin. It is for this reason that WAVE is intended to be used as an approximation tool which is then verified by dyno testing at a later stage.

The literature review of this study has revealed that some parts of the world may already be in a position where running E85 is beneficial as a whole, this is in terms of performance, cost-effectiveness, as well as being more environmentally friendly and sustainable. However, this is not the case for the entire planet as of yet. Countries like the UK have obstacles to overcome before this is the case, as land is not in abundance, E85 currently stands as a performance fuel for areas like motorsport where it is best utilised.

In terms of performance benefits overall, the study data has indicated a potential for E85 to be a viable fuel in a flex-fuel vehicle when better performance is desired. In order to confirm the theory explained by (HP Academy, 2023), further study into the chosen test engine and WAVE engine model is to be carried out. A comparison between current yielded results and results gained from a high-compression and forced induction engine is likely to indicate more notable trends and benefits of high-Ethanol fuels where knock-limitation is absolutely apparent.

With these considerations made, it is reasonable to conclude that E10 currently outperforms E85 in a real-world environment for this particular engine with its' relative state of tune. This is not definitive data as explained in the recommendations section, where a well-trained ECU calibrator has the potential to yield better performance results. With this aside, WAVE simulations as well as literature evidence has clearly indicated that E85 has the potential to be the better performing fuel overall. As it is only currently marginally outperforming the E10 fuel withing WAVE, further adjustments to the engine model and running conditions will allow for more well-defined margins between results.

In conclusion, the results of the study show E85 as a viable contender for a sustainable and well-performing fuel of the future. As the demand for finite resources increases, research and testing will force high-volume production of alternate fuels which will in turn reduce manufacturing costs and thus make obtaining E85 at the pump a more realistic option.

9. Recommendations

As part of an extensive list of recommendations made if the study were to be repeated, in terms of the practical testing, further hardware requirements consist of: wideband oxygen sensor feedback to ECU, knock-detection sensors, a safer testing environment (non-educational), outsourcing of a knowledgeable professional ECU calibrator, and a potentially sacrificial engine to be used in case of the event of total engine failure. On the simulation front, the main recommendation would be to source a near-identical performing model from the engine manufacturer/supplier. This would be used to initiate the investigation before making any modifications to account for alternative fuel types.

From a physical testing standpoint, there are several recommendations that are discussed in the text above that would be almost essential in improving the quality of the results for this experiment. Initially, the addition of safety and calibration hardware is vital in ensuring the best performance of the engine whilst still maintaining safe operating conditions for the engine. This can be achieved with the addition of knock sensors on the engine which can feedback any harmful detonation to the engine management software and ECU calibrator. Secondly, a wideband oxygen sensor that is able to feedback data into the engine ECU is necessary. This is in order to make use of target AFR tables and will not only makes tuning the ECU for fuel better but also allows the ECU to data-log information during a sweep test. This is vital in outlining any running issues that may be incurred due to poor fuelling or ignition settings, along with highlighting any other oversights.

The following recommendation falls within the environmental category. As burning fuel emits harmful gasses into the atmosphere; whether in small or large quantities is dependent on the fuel, but it is still beneficial to reduce the overall volume of fuel being burnt. This in turn would yield a lower environmental impact throughout the course of the study. The majority of testing can be carried out using WAVE software instead, which can then be tested/verified using the engine dyno afterwards in order to compare data and prove a hypothesis.

The next experimental recommendation involves using engine and dyno equipment outside of the educational environment wherever possible. By doing this, the risk to other individuals is reduced, and the tests can therefore be run under more realistic conditions. This may be at higher engine speeds with higher loads being applied to yield true performance values. The second advantage to this change is that the fear and risk of damaging University assets is reduced. Therefore, allowing for more thorough tests to be carried out, which in turn yield truer output values.

The final recommendation to be noted when considering physical engine testing is that of ECU calibration. With a greater budget allowance, an ECU calibration expert could be consulted. This can further reduce engine run-time and save on both costs and emissions incurred by running the dyno. This is because experienced calibration experts are able to advise on areas of an ECU map where a particular engine may prefer richer or leaner burn conditions. They are also able to identify where more or less aggressive ignition timing is advantageous, based on tuning for different fuels. This knowledge is gained through the experience and practise of working with the same engines and conditions on a regular basis, and can offset potential extra costs that would be incurred from running fuel through the engine for longer periods.

On the simulation testing section of this study, it would be beneficial for the majority of experimentation to be carried out on WAVE simulation software wherever possible, as it is the more cost-effective method of testing. This is due to several factors, mainly being the cost of purchasing the fuel. As E85 is currently not widely available in the UK, it works out at approximately £5.50/litre excluding delivery costs, whereas E10 pump fuel can currently be sourced for approximately £1.38/litre depending on the region. E10 is also easily accessible at any petrol station. E85 again incurs the added costs of delivery from a premium fuel supplier, as well as the added lead time required when considering fuel delivery times. Drop-shipping timing of the fuel is dependent on other factors such as availability and reliability of couriers as well.

Another major cost to note is that of maintaining the physical engine and dyno. The more hours that the equipment is placed under stress during testing, the greater the chances of wear and damage to the hardware. This in turn leads to extra costs to maintain and repair the equipment. This can therefore be reduced/avoided through the use of simulation software. As the software running costs are minimal, in addition to the low risk factor, it would be more beneficial to use WAVE as the primary testing environment. Simulation results can then be verified with the use of the engine dyno.

On the topic of software simulation, it would be beneficial to obtain a final version of the engine simulation from a manufacturer/engine developer as a base. This is in order to begin the tests with the closest possible parameters. This eliminates the need for investigations involving the initial WAVE data and engine dyno data through comparison at the start of the study.

Lastly, as mentioned previously, further testing with engines using higher compression ratios and forced induction would be beneficial to outline clear performance benefits of using E85. This is due to these engines being more naturally susceptible to knock limitation, as well as being more commonly found in high-performance environments such as motorsport.

As the combination of these recommendations allow for a more environmentally friendly approach with lower running costs and greater accuracy of results, they provide the most economical and ideal further steps in the study of alternative high-Ethanol fuels.

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11. Appendix

[1] – Existing dyno data obtained from a previous study carried out by student, using identical engine and dyno combination – Timmis, K (2021)

[2] – TunerStudios Software – Volumetric Efficiency Table (Low throttle, high RPM run case) – Author, 2023

[3] – TunerStudios Software – Ignition Advance Table (Low throttle, high RPM run case) – Author, 2023

Ignition Table 1 (Spark Advance)

View Help

i g n i t i o n a d v a n c e %	100.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	20.0	23.0	25.0	27.0	29.0	29.0	29.0	29.0
	95.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	20.0	23.0	25.0	27.0	29.0	29.0	29.0	29.0
	90.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	20.0	23.0	25.0	27.0	29.0	29.0	29.0	29.0
	80.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	21.0	24.0	26.0	29.0	30.0	30.0	30.0	30.0
	70.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	19.0	22.0	25.0	27.0	30.0	31.0	31.0	31.0	31.0
	60.0	14.0	14.0	15.0	20.0	23.0	26.0	29.0	31.0	32.0	32.0	32.0	32.0
	50.0	14.0	14.0	16.0	21.0	24.0	28.0	31.0	32.0	33.0	33.0	33.0	33.0
	40.0	14.0	14.0	17.0	22.0	27.0	31.0	33.0	34.0	34.0	34.0	34.0	34.0
	30.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	22.0	28.0	33.0	35.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0
	5.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	22.0	28.0	33.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0
	1.5	14.0	14.0	18.0	19.0	24.0	26.0	28.0	28.0	28.0	28.0	28.0	28.0
	T P 1.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0
		800	1000	1500	2000	2700	3400	4000	4600	5200	5700	7000	7200

rpm

Burn Close

[4] – TunerStudio Software - Fuel Volumetric Efficiency Table (Original E10 Tune) – Author (2022)

Fuel VE Table 1

View Tools Help

f u e l v o l u m e t r i c e f f i c i e n c y %	100.0	90	90	90	90	90	90	89	88	85	85	89	92	95	96	95	91	
	90.0	90	90	90	90	90	90	89	87	83	84	88	91	93	94	93	89	
	80.0	90	90	90	90	90	90	88	86	83	83	87	90	91	91	90	85	
	70.0	89	89	89	89	89	88	87	85	83	82	84	86	87	87	85	79	
	60.0	88	88	88	87	87	86	85	83	81	80	80	80	80	80	78	75	70
	50.0	86	86	86	86	84	83	82	80	78	78	76	75	72	70	67	62	
	45.0	84	84	84	83	82	79	78	75	74	72	70	67	65	62	59	53	
	40.0	81	81	80	79	63	75	72	68	65	63	61	58	55	52	49	44	
	30.0	79	79	78	75	73	70	66	62	58	55	53	49	46	44	41	37	
	25.0	76	76	75	71	66	62	58	54	50	47	45	42	39	37	34	31	
	20.0	70	68	66	63	50	53	50	46	43	40	38	35	33	31	29	27	
	15.0	63	61	58	53	48	44	40	37	35	32	30	28	26	25	23	21	
	10.0	54	52	47	35	40	34	32	30	28	26	24	23	21	20	19	18	
4.0	48	45	40	35	25	28	25	24	21	19	17	16	15	15	15	14		
T P S 1.5	40	36	32	26	22	20	18	17	16	13	12	12	12	12	12	12		
1.0	22	18	26	28	10	14	12	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11		
	600	800	1100	1400	1800	2200	2500	3000	3500	4000	4500	5000	5500	6000	7000	7200		

rpm

Burn Close

[5] – TunerStudio Software – Ignition Timing Advance Table (Original E10 Tune) – Author (2022)

Ignition Table 1 (Spark Advance)

View Help

i	100.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	20.0	23.0	25.0	27.0	29.0	29.0	29.0	29.0
g	95.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	20.0	23.0	25.0	27.0	29.0	29.0	29.0	29.0
n	90.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	20.0	23.0	25.0	27.0	29.0	29.0	29.0	29.0
l	80.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	21.0	24.0	26.0	29.0	30.0	30.0	30.0	30.0
o	70.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	19.0	22.0	25.0	27.0	30.0	31.0	31.0	31.0	31.0
a	60.0	14.0	14.0	15.0	20.0	23.0	26.0	29.0	31.0	32.0	32.0	32.0	32.0
d	50.0	14.0	14.0	16.0	21.0	24.0	28.0	31.0	32.0	33.0	33.0	33.0	33.0
	40.0	14.0	14.0	17.0	28.0	27.0	31.0	33.0	34.0	34.0	34.0	34.0	34.0
%	30.0	14.0	14.0	18.0	28.0	28.0	33.0	35.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0
	5.0	14.0	14.0	20.0	25.0	28.0	33.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0
	1.5	14.0	14.0	18.0	29.0	24.0	26.0	28.0	28.0	28.0	28.0	28.0	28.0
.	1.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	10.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0
P		800	1000	1500	2000	2700	3400	4000	4600	5200	5700	7000	7200

rpm

[6] – TunerStudio Software - Fuel Volumetric Efficiency Table (Final E85 Tune) – Author (2022)

Fuel VE Table 1

View Tools Help

f	100.0	126	126	126	126	126	126	125	123	119	119	125	129	133	134	133	127
u	90.0	126	126	126	126	126	126	125	122	116	118	123	127	130	132	130	125
e	80.0	126	126	126	126	126	126	123	120	116	116	122	126	127	127	126	119
l	70.0	125	125	125	125	125	123	122	119	116	115	118	120	122	122	119	111
l	60.0	123	123	123	122	122	120	119	116	113	112	112	112	112	109	105	98
o	50.0	120	120	120	120	118	116	115	112	109	109	106	105	101	98	94	87
a	45.0	118	118	118	116	113	111	109	105	104	101	98	94	91	87	83	74
d	40.0	113	113	112	113	115	116	101	95	91	88	85	81	77	73	69	62
	30.0	111	111	107	104	100	108	92	87	81	77	74	69	64	62	57	52
%	25.0	106	106	105	99	92	87	81	76	70	66	63	59	55	52	48	43
	20.0	98	95	92	87	90	86	69	64	60	56	53	49	46	43	41	38
	15.0	88	85	81	74	67	62	56	52	49	45	42	39	36	35	32	29
T	10.0	100	95	80	70	76	58	50	50	39	36	34	32	29	28	27	25
P	4.0	67	60	53	55	31	39	35	34	29	27	24	22	21	21	21	20
S	1.5	56	50	43	36	31	28	25	24	22	18	17	17	17	17	17	17
	1.0	42	25	36	39	14	20	17	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
		600	800	1100	1400	1800	2200	2500	3000	3500	4000	4500	5000	5500	6000	7000	7200

rpm

[7] – TunerStudio Software – Ignition Timing Advance Table (Final E85 Tune) – Author (2022)

	800	1000	1500	2000	2700	3400	4000	4600	5200	5700	7000	7200
100.0	17.0	17.0	17.0	20.0	22.0	25.0	27.0	29.0	31.0	31.0	31.0	31.0
95.0	17.0	17.0	17.0	20.0	22.7	25.0	27.0	29.0	31.0	31.0	31.0	31.0
90.0	17.0	17.0	17.0	20.0	23.4	25.0	27.0	29.0	31.0	31.0	31.0	31.0
80.0	17.0	17.0	17.0	20.0	24.9	26.0	28.0	31.0	32.0	32.0	32.0	32.0
70.0	17.0	17.0	17.0	21.0	26.3	27.0	29.0	32.0	33.0	33.0	33.0	33.0
60.0	17.0	17.0	18.5	22.0	27.7	28.0	31.0	33.0	34.0	34.0	34.0	34.0
50.0	17.0	17.0	20.0	23.0	29.1	30.0	33.0	34.0	35.0	35.0	35.0	35.0
40.0	17.0	17.0	24.0	24.0	30.6	33.0	35.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0	36.0
30.0	17.0	17.0	23.0	28.0	32.0	29.0	31.0	32.0	32.0	32.0	32.0	32.0
5.0	17.0	17.0	22.0	24.4	27.7	31.0	32.0	32.0	32.0	32.0	32.0	32.0
1.5	14.4	16.2	20.6	28.0	21.5	22.0	24.0	24.0	24.0	24.0	24.0	24.0
1.0	14.0	12.7	13.9	15.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0

[8] – TunerStudio Software – Air-to-Fuel Ratio Target Table – Author (2022)

	500	800	1200	1400	2000	2600	3100	3700	4300	4900	5400	6000
110.0	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7
100.0	12.9	12.9	12.9	12.9	12.9	12.9	12.9	12.9	12.9	12.9	12.9	12.9
90.0	12.9	12.9	12.9	13.1	13.1	13.1	13.1	13.1	13.1	13.1	13.1	13.1
80.0	13.1	13.1	13.1	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3
70.0	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.5	13.5	13.5	13.5	13.5	13.5	13.5	13.5	13.5
60.0	13.6	13.6	13.6	13.7	13.7	13.7	13.7	13.7	13.7	13.7	13.7	13.7
50.0	13.8	13.8	13.8	13.9	13.9	13.9	13.9	13.9	13.9	13.9	13.9	13.9
40.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.2	14.2	14.2	14.2	14.2	14.2	14.2	14.2	14.2
30.0	14.4	14.4	14.4	14.5	14.5	14.5	14.5	14.5	14.5	14.3	14.3	14.3
20.0	14.6	14.6	14.6	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.5	14.4	14.4
10.0	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.5	14.4	14.4
0.0	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.5	14.4	14.4